

DIGITAL LITERACY AS A KEY COMPONENT IN LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES FOR MODERN PROFESSIONS.

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Abstract The aim of this thesis is to find out the significance of digital literacy in learning foreign languages for modern professions. Digital skills and foreign language competence have become increasingly important in the education and world of work in today's technological society. The research examines the role of digital technologies in language learning and professional communication. The study also provides an account of the benefits of the learning platforms used online and the interactive educational tools. The results suggest that digital literacy enhances the efficiency of language learning and equips students with the necessary skills to be successful in the global job market.

Keywords: digital literacy, foreign language, modern professions, technology, internet education, communication

Аннотация Цель данной тезисной работы — изучить значение цифровой грамотности в изучении иностранных языков для современных профессий. В современном технологическом обществе цифровые навыки и владение иностранными языками стали важными как в образовании, так и в профессиональной деятельности. В исследовании рассматривается роль цифровых технологий в изучении языков и профессиональной коммуникации. Также освещаются преимущества онлайн-платформ обучения и интерактивных образовательных инструментов. Результаты исследования показывают, что цифровая грамотность повышает эффективность изучения языков и обеспечивает студентов необходимыми навыками для успешной деятельности на глобальном рынке труда.

Ключевые слова: цифровая грамотность, иностранный язык, современные профессии, технологии, интернет-образование, коммуникация.

Annotatsiya Ushbu tezisning maqsadi zamonaviy kasblar uchun xorijiy tillarni o'rganishda raqamli savodxonlikning ahamiyatini o'rganishdan iborat. Bugungi texnologik jamiyatda raqamli ko'nikmalar va xorijiy til kompetensiyasi ta'lim hamda kasbiy faoliyatda muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Tadqiqotda raqamli texnologiyalarning til o'rganish va professional muloqotdagi o'rni tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, onlayn ta'lim platformalari va interaktiv ta'lim vositalarining afzalliklari yoritib beriladi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, raqamli savodxonlik til o'rganish samaradorligini oshiradi va talabalarni global mehnat bozorida muvaffaqiyatga erishish uchun zarur ko'nikmalar bilan ta'minlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli savodxonlik, xorijiy til, zamonaviy kasblar, texnologiya, internet ta'limi, muloqot.

The world today is technology-driven and in today's world, technology is a part of education and in the professional world. One of the 21st Century skills is digital literacy. The

importance of language learning in communication, academic achievement and career development cannot be ignored at the same time. Today many jobs demand specialists to utilize the digital technologies and to be able to communicate effectively in foreign languages. This topic is relevant to the rise in the use of online technologies in language learning. Students study with the help of their smartphones, computers and the internet today. But having technology is not enough for effective learning; it's just as important that these technologies be used effectively. The primary goal of this research is to examine the role of digital literacy in the foreign language learning and its importance for the new professions.

Digital literacy is defined as the capability to use digital devices, platforms and information technologies effectively. Digital tools can be used in foreign language instruction to enhance listening, speaking, reading and writing skills with interactive activities and via Internet communication. Descriptive and comparative method were employed in the conduct of the research. Analysis of scientific articles, educational websites, and digital learning platform to gain insight into the effect of technology on language learning. Many students have these vocabulary and grammar learning apps today—Duolingo and Quizlet. These sites offer interactive practice, pronunciation and instant feedback. For instance, English learners can practice speaking by having conversations online with Zoom or Microsoft Teams. These technologies provide a possibility of communication with native speakers and international students. Further, digital platforms such as Google Classroom are used to plan lessons and tasks in educational institutions. Presentations, video and quizzes are uploaded and students can work and get feedback online. This simplifies the learning process and makes it more flexible. Digital literacy also plays a role in the knowledge-based fields of business, tourism, healthcare, IT, and others. For example, in international companies, people work in English with emails, on-line meetings and digital presentations. Those who have both language and digital skills are more competitive in the global job market. The study reveals that students' communication skills, motivation, and academic achievement are more positive when they learn languages by using digital technologies.

Digital literacy is an important factor in learning foreign languages for modern professions in general.

Technology enhances learning opportunities and education quality, and provides more opportunities for independent and interactive learning. Students' foreign language competence and digital skills equip them to meet the demands of the modern workplace.

The contributions of this research to the practical aspect of language teaching are able to motivate the educational institutions to use digital technology as a means in language teaching. Enhancing students' digital and language abilities can open up more career prospects and prepare them for future work

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